

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14446306

Impact of Mobile Learning Technologies on Students Academic Performance Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher formulated two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses that guided the conduct of the study. The research design used for the study is descriptive survey research design. The target population of the study was all the 534 Students in School of Information and Communication Technology, in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rivers State. The sample of the study was 534 students. The sampling technique used was a census method of sampling. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled, "Impact of Mobile Learning Technologies on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire". The data generated were analyzed using mean and standard deviation (SD) to answer research questions. Items that scored $x \geq 2.50$ were agreed whereas those below it disagreed. T-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. Based on the data analysis, the findings of the study revealed that mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that: school management should officially adopt the uses of smartphones device since it enhance students' academic performance and school management should organize seminar programme for the students to educate them on the uses of personal digital assistants' device because of its enhancement on students' academic performance.

Keywords: Impact, Mobile Learning, Technologies, Personal Digital Assistants, Smartphones

INTRODUCTION

Mobile learning (m-learning) currently is a well-established methodology. It has been in use for almost 20 years and its use offers an anytime and anywhere method of learning. Nearly all university students in developed countries possess some kind of mobile device and 50% of them possess more than one. The most used mobile devices among young people appear to be smartphones (Zhu, 2022). The largest group as far as the use and ownership is concerned is young adults between 18 years and 29 years. This fact has

been also confirmed by other research studies conducted among university students. In fact, students of tertiary education are a focus group in the context of this study.

Mobile learning, also referred to as mLearning, is a way of accessing learning content through mobile devices. This method empowers learning at the point of need, enabling users to access content whenever and wherever suits them. Sharp (2015) observed that the most important element of mobile learning is its focus on the mobility of the learner - giving them the ability to choose when and where they want to access learning means that they can go at their own pace, increasing engagement and improving knowledge retention.

M learning is the use of mobile technology like smartphones for educational purposes. Short for mobile learning, the term M learning encompasses all learning through apps, mobile browsers, tablets and more. Over the past 15 years, the use of mobile technology in education has risen enormously as people use their smartphones to both learn and teach remotely (Coie & Dodge, 2018). M learning is convenient, quick and ideal for our on-the-go lifestyles and the trend doesn't look like it's slowing down soon. In 2022, we're officially living in a mobile-first economy. Billions of people across the world now use smartphones every day for tasks ranging from gaming to dating and everything in between. M-Learning is learning accomplished with the use of small, portable computing devices. These computing devices may include: smartphones, personal digital assistants (PDAs) and similar handheld devices (Leary, 2020).

Impact of Smartphones Devices on Learning in Higher Education

Smartphone is carried on the person so it is accessible anywhere and at anytime. This makes accessing learning content easy, regardless of the location or the time of day. So, students can have access to the tools that expand their learning without interruption. Smartphones have become an ingrained aspect in the lives of students. When talking about benefits, it's important to appreciate that smartphones enable students to learn through a medium that they find most comfortable. With this in mind, let's take a look at those benefits the smartphone provides to extend learning opportunities for students (Daramola, 2014).

1. Anytime, Anywhere: First and foremost, the smartphone is carried on the person so it is accessible anywhere and at anytime. This makes accessing learning content easy, regardless of the location or the time of day. So, students can have access to the tools that expand their learning without interruption. Learning is available, literally at their fingertips.

2. Collaboration: The scope of the mobile phone to synchronise communication makes it an exceptional social tool and can enhance collaboration between students, teachers, parents, and the wider school community. With the smartphone, social interaction is enhanced and keeps the school community connected at all times.

3. Ownership of Learning: Mobile learning allows multiple mediums for engagement that can be tailored to suit individual preferences. This aspect of mobile learning provides students the opportunity to take control of their education and develop a sense of ownership. Having options gives students the choice to learn through mediums they are most comfortable with and thereby enhance the learning journey altogether (Romer, 2013).

4. Accessible, Portable Learning Aid: Readily available and easy to access, we are living in a world where the smartphone is prevalent in every household. Whether or not there is a laptop, tablet, or a desktop, you can be 99.9% sure that there will be a smartphone. Being a common presence throughout households of all demographics, the smartphone provides a portable platform that makes for a powerful learning aid.

5. A Platform for Practical Tools: Last but not least, the mobile phone can compute and display content that is personal and tailored to the individual with ease. So, applications that contain geo-location, social networking, search functions, newsreaders, and simulations can be effortlessly customised to provide practical learning tools on the smartphone.

Students are more willing to participate in learning when educational content is delivered in an interactive and dynamic way through quizzes, polls, surveys, and videos. And the smartphone greatly assists and

supports this type of delivery. Mobile learning offers great opportunities to enhance the education of young learners by blending with traditional methods (Douglas, 2018). This blended-learning approach can be extremely effective when the role of the smartphone in the learning journey is properly understood. Learning with the smartphone has been found to be highly effective for vocabulary practice, brainstorming, self-reflection, feedback on performance and more recently, augmented reality.

Impact of Personal Digital Assistants Devices on Learning in Higher Education

Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs), like laptops, were used in participatory simulations to test their effectiveness as a teaching tool. Participatory simulations are activities that teach by embedding learners in lifelike role playing scenarios. A Personal Digital Assistant is a handheld mobile device sometimes known as a Palm, can be used a phone or minicomputer. Using either a touchscreen or stylus, users enter data on office software such as address books, email, or schedule planners. According to Erica (2016) a Personal Digital Assistant is a handheld mobile device sometimes known as a Palm, can be used a phone or minicomputer. Using either a touchscreen or stylus, users enter data on office software such as address books, email, or schedule planners. First-generation PDAs were considered simply electronic versions of paper-based PIMs. These PDAs allowed for the convenient organization of calendar items (meeting reminders) and served as contact organizers and notepads. With each successive generation, PDAs have slowly evolved into true portable computing companions. Currently, there are two dominant PDA operating system (OSs).

Features useful for teaching

Many PDA features can be advantageous for teaching. I find that having a single PDA device allows for convenient access to teaching material and facilitates spontaneous teaching opportunities (Edoh & Iyamu, 2022). The PDA features I routinely rely on for teaching include file storage, database capabilities, electronic presentation viewing, and access to e-books. A feature that I find useful but underused is PDAs' ability to function as file repositories. Personal digital assistants can replace separate storage media. Personal digital assistants are convenient mobile tools with robust technology and applications that are exceptionally suited for health professional educators such as myself. The future of PDAs is very promising. We will see more advanced PDAs, integrating an assortment of components allowing health professionals to be effective educators as well as learners. In the near future, PDAs will have faster and more efficient central processing units, increasing their speed and offering longer.

A personal digital assistant (PDA) is a multi-purpose mobile device which functions as a personal information manager. Following a boom in the 1990s and 2000s, PDA's were mostly displaced by the widespread adoption of more highly capable smartphones, in particular those based on iOS and Android in the late 2000's, and thus saw a rapid decline. A PDA has an electronic visual display. Most models also have audio capabilities, allowing usage as a portable media player, and also enabling many of them to be used as telephones (Hastings, 2013). By the early 2000s, nearly all PDA models had the ability to access the Internet, intranets or extranets via Wi-Fi or Wireless WANs, and since then generally included a web browser. Sometimes, instead of buttons, later PDAs employ touchscreen technology.

Key characteristics of Mobile Learning

There are several key characteristics which make mobile learning so effective for training dispersed workforces:

Microlearning content: Mobile learning is often used to deliver microlearning content: 2-5 minute bursts of relevant information designed to maintain learners' attention and bolster knowledge retention. Microlearning content works by replicating the content we consume daily via our social media feeds, leveraging short form video, animation, gamification, quizzes and more interactive formats to better engage the modern workforce.

Social learning: Also with the aim of replicating online behaviors, mobile learning often utilizes social learning to boost engagement. This might include a forum, newsfeed or chat function for learners to ask each other questions, connect with peers and share their insights.

Seamless access: Though not provided by all mLearning platforms, seamless access is fast becoming a crucial element of mobile-based training solutions. Whether it's removing the login process with seamless links or embedding content directly into your native app, removing this friction vastly increases engagement and makes training even more accessible for learners on the go.

Benefits of Mobile Learning

- 1. Flexibility:** One of the key advantages of m learning is the flexibility it gives your students. Learning is easily integrated into every day, rather than being a special event. M learning is self-paced so your students can move through the course content at their own speed, in whatever setting, time zone or schedule that works for them.
- 2. Convenience:** Students can access your course content from anywhere and at any time. They don't have to be at home sat in front of their desktop to engage with your content – they can complete modules on their commute, while they're standing in line for coffee, at the grocery store and more. This means learning can move across a range of different environments and social spaces, boosting the convenience and practicality of taking an online course and opening up your course to more people (Hinshaw, 2022).
- 3. Usability:** For many people, m learning is easier to use than other forms of learning. It's instinctive, quick and new knowledge is just a tap or finger touch away. No textbooks, notebooks or keyboard needed. Anyone with a mobile device and an internet connection can learn, whatever their age, location or background.
- 4. Social Learning:** M learning makes it easy for learners to connect with other students, including via social media, your membership platform or through in-app features. Students can ask questions, share updates on their progress and start discussions. With m learning, social learning becomes seamless, providing opportunities for collaboration and more personalized learning experiences throughout your course.
- 5. Knowledge Retention:** There is some evidence that m learning can boost knowledge retention compared to regular learning styles, helping your course content to stick in your students' heads. Rather than just watching you teach, with m learning students have a wider range of opportunities to test and apply their knowledge.
- 6. Engagement:** With the right course design, m learning can also make the learning experience more interesting, dynamic and fun. The mobile learning format opens up new opportunities for gamified elements in your course content, like quick quizzes, competitions and more. M learning can boost learners' feeling of achievement, enjoyment and engagement by making course content more accessible with gamification (Klem & Connell, 2014).
- 7. Support and Feedback:** Many m learning platforms also allow for instant feedback and support, making it easier and faster for students to receive feedback on their work, raise issues and get answers. This helps boost learner motivation, confidence and understanding of the content.
- 8. Habit Formation:** For some students, m learning could also make it easier to form a routine or learning habit. With mobile learning, all your course content is in your students' pockets, they just have to pick up their phone and log in.

Statement of the Problem

Traditional teaching methods are often characterised by teacher-centred instruction. They focus on textbooks and lectures and have been the predominant approach in education for many years. Their effectiveness can vary depending on the context, subject matter, and individual learners. Traditional teaching methods are characterised by teacher-centred lectures, textbooks, and standardised assessments. They have been an educational mainstay for centuries.

Studies carried out by Bassey (2017) and Nelson (2021) showed that traditional teaching methods have some limitations in today's evolving world and have limited student engagement. Noting that traditional methods can lead to passive learning. So students become recipients of information. And don't be active participants in the learning process. This lack of engagement can hinder deeper understanding and retention. We have lacks of a real-world connection. Traditional methods often fail to connect learning to real-world applications. It makes it difficult for students to see the relevance of what they are learning. Lacks Personalisation, traditional methods may not cater to individual learning styles and paces. Students come with diverse learning preferences and abilities. They may find it challenging to thrive in a one-size-fits-all approach.

We also have contrasts between memorisation and understanding. Traditional methods often emphasise memorisation. They focus on recalling facts. They don't promote deeper understanding and critical thinking skills. This can result in surface-level comprehension. And may not be applicable in real-world scenarios. Use of Technology is Limited. Traditional teaching methods may not fully leverage the benefits of modern technology. It is an era where technology plays a significant role in various aspects of life. The limited integration of tech tools in traditional methods can be a disadvantage. Not flexible, traditional methods can be rigid and inflexible. They make it challenging to adapt to the evolving needs of learners. They don't incorporate innovative teaching approaches. This lack of flexibility may hinder the development of creative and adaptable thinking. has a potential for boredom, the lack of variety in traditional methods can lead to student boredom. Because the lessons primarily involve lectures and textbooks. So students may become disinterested, affecting their motivation and enthusiasm for learning. Traditional teaching methods often place a strong emphasis on grades and standardised testing. This focus can create a competitive atmosphere. It may lead to a prioritisation of grades over a genuine understanding of the material and traditional methods may not adequately address the development of essential life skills. It includes critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and communication. These are increasingly valued in the modern world. It is against this bedrock that the study examined the impact of mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Higher Institution in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State. In specific terms the study focussed on the following objectives:

1. To examine the extent to which smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.
- 2 To determine the extent to which personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State?
- 2 To what extent does personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses:

- 1 There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.
- 2 There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used as the design of the study. Victor (2012), asserts that the purpose of the design was to determine the impact of mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance. The target population of the study was all the 534 Students in School of Information and Communication Technology, in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rivers State. 151 students in Computer Science Department, 83 in Library and Information Management Department and 300 students in Department of Mass Communication. The sample of the study was 534 students. The sampling technique used was a census method of sampling. The entire population size of 534 students were used for the sample size because of the manageability of the population size. A census method is that process of sampling or statistical list where all members of a population are analyzed or used. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled, "Impact of Mobile Learning Technologies on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire" (IMLTSAPO). The data generated were analyzed using mean and standard deviation (SD) to answer research questions. Items that scored $x \geq 2.50$ were agreed whereas those below it disagreed. T-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rivers State?*

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic

S/No.	Statement	Male Students =184			Female Students =350		
		\bar{X}	SD	D	\bar{X}	SD	D
1	Smartphone is accessible anywhere and at anytime	3.13	0.88	High Extent	3.09	0.88	High Extent
2	Smartphone makes accessing learning content easy	3.07	0.87	High Extent	3.03	0.87	High Extent
3	Smartphones have become an ingrained aspect in the lives of students	3.22	0.90	High Extent	3.18	0.89	High Extent
4	Students can have access to the tools that expand their learning without interruption	3.09	0.88	High Extent	3.01	0.87	High Extent
5	Smartphone extend learning opportunities for students	3.15	0.81	High Extent	3.11	0.88	High Extent
Grand Mean/ Standard Deviation		3.05	0.87		3.07	0.89	

Table 1 presents that items 1 to 5 have means of 3.13, 3.07, 3.22, 3.09, 3.15 for male students with standard deviations ranging from 0.88 to 0.81 and means of 3.09, 3.03, 3.18, 3.01, 3.11 for female students with standard deviations ranging from 0.85 to 0.94 which indicate "High Extent" on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. Also, the grand means for male students and female students are 3.57 and 2.91 respectively, further confirming a "High Extent" on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. Thus, it is found that smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rivers State?*

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic

S/No.	Statement	Male Students =184			Female Students =350		
		\bar{X}	SD	D	\bar{X}	SD	D
6	Personal Digital Assistants are used in participatory simulations to test students effectiveness as a teaching tool	2.97	0.86	High Extent	3.03	0.87	High Extent
7	Personal Digital Assistant is a handheld mobile device used to foster learning	2.87	0.85	High Extent	2.71	0.82	High Extent
8	Personal digital assistants are convenient mobile tools with robust technology	3.02	0.87	High Extent	2.94	0.86	High Extent
9	It has applications that are exceptionally suited for health professional educators such as myself	3.06	0.87	High Extent	3.20	0.73	High Extent
10	PDA's have faster and more efficient central processing units	2.89	0.85	High Extent	2.94	0.82	High Extent
Grand Mean/ Standard Deviation		3.57	0.94		2.91	0.85	

The information in table 2 shows that items 6 to 10 have means of 2.97, 2.87, 3.02, 3.06, 2.89 for male students with standard deviations ranging from 0.86 to 0.85; and means of 3.03, 2.71, 2.94, 2.88, 3.01 for female students with standard deviations ranging from 0.88 to 0.88 indicating a "High Extent" on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. The grand means for male students and female students are, respectively, 3.08 and 3.13, which is a confirmation of "High Extent" on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. The above results imply that personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23 was used for the test of hypotheses. The t-test (rather than the z-test) statistic was employed in the analysis despite the large sample size. This was so for three major reasons: 1. When the sample is sufficiently large, the t-value and the z-value coincide. 2. The SPSS does not contain the z-test as both z-test and t-test are treated as the same for sufficiently large samples. 3. Very importantly, the t-value is computed when the population mean and standard deviation are not known, but for z-value computation, the population mean and standard deviation must be known.

The symbols used here were as specified below:

- F = Ratio of homogeneity between group variance to within group variance (Levene's Test for Equality of Variances)
- t = Value of t-statistic obtained from the SPSS analysis
- df = Degrees of freedom
- p-value = Sig. (2-tailed) obtained from the SPSS analysis to be compared with the α -value
- α -value = Level of significance (0.050) fixed by Rivers State University

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of the significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State

	F	Sig.	T	Df	p-value	α -value	Decision
Equal variances assumed	70.709	.110	-2.577	798	.072	.050	H ₀ Not Rejected
Equal variances not assumed			-2.577	728.206	.072	.050	

Table 3 presents that equal variances assumed has $t = -2.577$, $df = 798$, and 2-tailed $p = 0.072$. This implies that the null hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State" is not rejected as $t(798) = -2.577$, 2-tailed $p = 0.072 > \alpha = 0.05$. Thus, male and female students of Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic are in accordance that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent smartphones device enhance students' academic performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of the significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State

	F	Sig.	T	Df	p-value	α -value	Decision
Equal variances assumed	1.085	.298	4.251	798	.107	.050	H ₀ Not Rejected
Equal variances not assumed			4.251	796.709	.107	.050	

The information in table 4 shows that equal variances assumed has $t = 4.251$, $df = 798$, and 2-tailed $p = 0.107$. Thus, the null hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State" is not rejected as $t(798) = 4.251$, 2-tailed $p = 0.107 > \alpha = 0.05$. This implies that male and female students in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State are in agreement that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the extent personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Extent Smartphones Device Enhance Students' Academic Performance

The finding of the study in research question one revealed that smartphones device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. The study still showed that smartphone is carried on the person so it is accessible anywhere and at anytime. This finding is in line with Douglas (2018) who asserts that smartphones makes accessing learning content easy, regardless of the location or the time of day. So, students can have access to the tools that expand their learning without interruption. Smartphones have become an ingrained aspect in the lives of students. When talking about benefits, it's important to appreciate that smartphones enable students to learn through a medium that they find most

comfortable. With this in mind, let's take a look at those benefits the smartphone provides to extend learning opportunities for students.

Extent Personal Digital Assistants' Device Enhance Students' Academic Performance

In research question two, the findings also showed that the personal digital assistants' device enhance students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic. This finding is in the same view with Leary (2020) who admitted that Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs), like laptops, were used in participatory simulations to test their effectiveness as a teaching tool. Participatory simulations are activities that teach by embedding learners in lifesize role playing scenarios. A Personal Digital Assistant is a handheld mobile device sometimes known as a Palm, can be used a phone or minicomputer. Using either a touchscreen or stylus, users enter data on office software such as address books, email, or schedule planners. A Personal Digital Assistant is a handheld mobile device sometimes known as a Palm, can be used a phone or minicomputer. Using either a touchscreen or stylus, users enter data on office software such as address books, email, or schedule planners.

CONCLUSION

The impact of mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State cannot be over emphasized. Based on the analysis, the study concludes that mobile learning technologies on students' academic performance in Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic Rivers State. The study still deduced that mobile learning is convenient, quick and ideal for our on-the-go lifestyles and the trend doesn't look like it's slowing down soon. In 2022, we're officially living in a mobile-first economy. Billions of people across the world now use smartphones every day for tasks ranging from gaming to dating and everything in between. M-Learning is learning accomplished with the use of small, portable computing devices. These computing devices may include: smartphones, personal digital assistants (PDAs) and similar handheld devices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby put forward to ensure that this study achieve its objectives.

1. School management should officially adopt the uses of smartphones device since it enhance students' academic performance.
2. School management should organize seminar programme for the students to educate them on the uses of personal digital assistants' device because of its enhancement on students' academic performance.

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